

ROLE OF AYURVEDIC CONSTITUTIONAL ASSESSMENT (PRAKRITI) IN HEALTH
PROMOTION AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT: A REVIEWDr. Mahendra Kumar Sourtha^{*1}, Dr. Jagdish Prasad Bairwa²¹Associate Professor, Department of Kriya Sharir, Government Ayurved College, Sikar, Rajasthan.²Associate Professor, Department of Rog Nidan, Government Ayurved College, Jaipur.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Mahendra Kumar Sourtha**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- Understanding prakriti is vital for general health and welfare, and maintaining a nutritious diet is crucial to avoiding future illnesses. "Ahara" (diet) and "Anna" (food) have received more attention in Ayurveda. A deeper comprehension of the Prakriti may lead an individual to pursue personalised preventative health for a better quality of life. Ayurveda holds that prakriti and health are vital for well-being and that eating a balanced diet can help prevent illnesses, leading to personalised preventative health and an improved quality of life. **Material and Method:** The *Laghutrayi*, the *Brihatrayi* and its commentaries, and other Ayurvedic and contemporary books were used to compile information on *prakriti parikshan*. **Result:** A person's food influences their genetic constitution, with *Prakriti* playing a major role in determining their general health, according to the ancient Ayurveda. Numerous studies have been conducted thus far, particularly in the fields of prakriti and pregnancy and prakriti, prakriti and metabolic health, prakriti and chronic illness, prakriti and neonatal genetic screening, and prakriti and genome. **Discussion:** To improve one's health, further research is required to examine the connection between nutrition and prakriti. The people of today are aware of food and nutrition, but understanding which diets are suitable for their Prakriti is essential to leading a fulfilling life. Diagnosing, treating, and avoiding a number of complex disorders requires an understanding of a patient's physical and mental composition through Prakriti analysis.

KEYWORDS: *Prakriti*, *Prakriti parikshan*, health, management.**INTRODUCTION**

The ancient medical system known as Ayurveda has been practiced on the Indian subcontinent for thousands of years. One of the fundamental principles of Ayurveda is the *tridosha*, a framework for understanding both health and illness.^[1] The idea of *tridosha*, which incorporates the three doshas of *vata*, *pitta*, and *kapha*, is one of the fundamental tenets of Ayurveda. It comes from the first chapter of the oldest Ayurvedic literature, the *Charaka Samhita*.^[2] The ancient Ayurvedic texts explain a variety of dosha traits and how they affect an individual's physiology or prakriti based on the dominance of one or more doshas. One can reasonably infer a person's mental inclinations, physical strengths and weaknesses, and susceptibility to specific types of illnesses from their prakriti. Ayurveda holds that *Prakriti* was established at

the beginning of human history and usually remains constant over time. The Sanskrit terms "Pra" and "Kriti" are the roots of the word "Prakriti." Pra denotes the starting point or place of origin, whereas Kriti describes the process of doing or generating. Therefore, the term Prakriti describes the actual state or nature of an individual. Prakriti is the manifestation or expression of an individual's physical, physiological, psychological, or social traits.^[3] Every individual has a distinct nature, according to Ayurveda. Each Prakriti person has a unique physical appearance according to their *Dosha* and *Mahabhuta* dominance at birth. Prakriti is a collection of physical attributes, both internal and external. *Prakriti* in humans is impacted by both hereditary and acquired variables.

REVIEW OF LITRETURE

Prakriti

The two halves of this constitution are the "mental body" and the "physical body." The term "prakriti" refers to an individual's "nature" or "natural constitution." *Pra* and *kriti* are both words that refer to the "beginning" or "source of origin." Prakriti is a combination of the Hindi words for "natural form." "*Prakriti*" comes from "*Prakarotiiti*." Prakriti, which is defined as the formation of unique attributes brought on by the dominance of the *Doshas* (*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*, the functional components of the body), denotes the presence of a specific *Dosha* in a human person. The makeup of a body is also influenced by other elements.^[4] Charaka lists additional elements that affect Prakriti, such as the time of year, the state of the uterus, the mother's diet during her pregnancy, various customs she engaged in, the mother and father's *Sukra-Sonita* (sperm-ovum), and *Mahabhuta Vikara*. These factors produce one or more of the *doshas* that are mostly linked to the previously listed features. As a result, some people's Prakriti is governed by *Vata*, others by *Pitta*, yet others by *Kapha*, and in other situations, the *Dosha* maintains equilibrium. While each of the aforementioned elements is significant while assessing Prakriti.^[5] In essence, Prakriti and lifestyle are natural occurrences. The dominating *Dosha* is a specific kind of Prakriti because the *Vata-Pitta*, *Kapha*, and *Manasika Doshas* (functional psychological elements) directly govern all physiological processes. Maintaining a manner of life that is in opposition to one's Prakriti and adhering to personal, moral, and seasonal conduct are the two guiding principles for keeping one's body and lifestyle in a suitable state of health. Healthy tissues and *Dosha* equilibrium result from adhering to Prakriti-based dietary and lifestyle guidelines.^[6] It is recommended that a person with a *Pitta*-predominant Prakriti, for instance, eat any food that causes their body temperature to rise. Adding more activities that generate heat to his already elevated body temperature could lead to a variety of ailments. We can only do this if we understand the Prakriti. Being aware of one's Prakriti will demonstrate one's ability to counteract lifestyle issues. Of the six types, Prakriti with one *Dosha*, or Prakriti composed of a single bodily humour, is more resilient than Prakriti with two *Doshas*, or Prakriti composed of two body humours.⁷ The order of Prakriti's susceptibility to *Vata-Pitta-Kapha* sickness is diminishing. Generally speaking, by understanding your Prakriti, you may adjust your lifestyle by learning the proper way to perform everyday duties and how to maintain your health by understanding the kind of problems or illnesses your body may face in the future. One notices a link between a lifestyle problem and a specific Prakriti. Ayurveda has established particular dietary guidelines that must be followed in order to prevent a variety of lifestyle problems, according to Prakriti type.

Understanding of humanity through Prakriti

The following facets of human existence can be used to understand the distinctions between different people with

the help of Prakriti. This allows a person to better understand themselves and live in harmony with their "nature," making their life more appropriate.^[8]

- Life span of an individual
- *Sadavritta* (Social life)
- Measuring of an individual
- To choose the perfect partner in marital affairs
- To choose an appropriate profession / occupation

Preventive and promotive health care according Prakriti

A person can improve their health and delay the start of many illnesses by being aware of their Prakriti. It helps with the observation and study of lifestyle styles and eating habits in addition to daily and seasonal routines. In accordance with one's Prakriti, Ayurveda also suggests certain foods and practices that one should follow to stay healthy and avoid certain ailments. to heed the counsel of *Dincharya* and *Ritucharya* and embrace a nutritious food and way of life.^[9]

Diagnosis of the diseases according Prakriti

Prakriti analysis is essential for treating the patient and determining the underlying conditions. Studying the Prakriti, which not only indicates the vitiated *Dosha* but also the therapy principles for that particular person, facilitates the diagnosis of a certain condition.^[10]

Prognosis of Health status according Prakriti

Prakriti divulges all aspect about a certain individual. As a result, we may assess his or her hunger, adaptability, body compactness, and mental and physical strength. Based on these findings, we can make some conclusions regarding the person's health.^[11]

Disease susceptibility and Prakriti

Each person in the universe has a unique Prakriti, or set of *Doshas*, within their body. People who lead unhealthy lives, eat poorly, or don't follow a Prakriti-appropriate routine may be more prone to illnesses caused by the same *Dosha* of their Prakriti. Furthermore, *Vata* persons should adhere to the food and lifestyle guidelines based on their Prakriti as they are more likely to have ailments, according to Ayurveda.

IMPORTANCE OF PRAKRITI TO DIAGNOSIS THE VYADHI

- **Promotion of health** - Ayurveda advises people to engage in activities and consume foods that are against their Prakriti in order to have healthy lives. When rejuvenating treatments like *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* are delivered in accordance with a person's Prakriti, the maximum advantages are achieved.
- **Analysis of bala according to prakriti**- The relative strengths of different people can be understood by looking at their Prakriti type. Those who are *Kapha* Prakriti are stronger than those who are *Pitta* or *Vata* Prakriti. When administering treatment, determining a patient's strength is crucial.

- **Vulnerability to vyadhi** - Each Prakriti type is prone to specific illnesses. A person's vulnerability to illnesses associated with a certain Dosha is determined by their Prakriti. For instance, *Agnimandhya, Pratishyaya, Medoroga, Prameha, and other Kaphaja Vikara* are more common in Kapha Prakriti individuals. Similarly, Vata Prakriti individuals are more susceptible to *Pittaja, Gulma, Aatopa*, and other negative effects. Prakriti persons are more likely to suffer from *Amlapitta, Pandu, Kaamla, Raktapitta*, and other illnesses.
- **Role of Prakriti in the management of vyadhi** – When treating a patient's illness, Acharya Charak explained the concept of "Prati-Purusha-siddhanta," which takes into account the patient's Prakriti in addition to other unique traits. Understanding Prakriti facilitates the process of deciding on a patient's course of treatment. In *Amamaja vyadhi*, such as *Jwara, a Kaphaja* person can embrace the complete *Apatarpana Chikitsa*, whereas a *Vataja* person cannot. The treatment plan is based on the body's tolerance to the medications. Prakriti exemplifies the types of foods, habits, and plants that will be helpful in the therapy of that person. With Prakriti's help, we are able to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the patient's appetite, preferences, mental and physical health, and capacity to adapt to new foods and drugs.

DISCUSSION

According to the Acharya *vagbhatta Prakriti* chapter, the *Doshik* constitution (predominance) that existed at birth remains unchanged from conception to death. According to Acharya Sushruta, Prakriti was created at the exact moment of conception, or the union of the male and female gametes. For instance, if a person's Vata dosha is greater than their Pitta and Kapha doshas at birth (both quantitatively and qualitatively), we call them *Vataja Prakriti*. An individual's anatomy, physiology, psychology, and immunity are all impacted by their predominant *vata dosha*. The characteristics and roles of the Vata Dosha are used to interpret features.^[12] Generally speaking, a person's lifestyle is the result of their physical and psychological characteristics taken together. Their routines, attitude, diet, and way of life all reflect this lifestyle, which is founded on the lessons they learnt as kids from their parents, siblings, peers, and other close family members. As a result, it calls for the regulation of only psychological and natural actions of the body and senses. Disruptions in these three processes—initiation, control, and coordination—lead to lifestyle derangement and other lifestyle disorders. According to Ayurveda, this episode was categorised as "*Pragyapradha*" (intellectual blasphemy), one of the three fundamental causes of all ailments.^[13] Suppressing any intrinsic urge is one of the many inappropriate habits that are the fundamental cause of many ailments that are caused by *Pranaparadha*. The fundamental causes of sickness are the reversal of any neurotransmission or the incorrect elimination of waste products generated during

metabolism, which results in a buildup of toxins. Thus, one of the main causes of lifestyle diseases may be the practice of suppressing desires in an unhealthy way of living. According to Charaka's concept of Ayurveda, the main course of treatment is to get rid of these accumulated waste products.^[14]

The Doshas require a specific diet in order to continue operating normally. Unhealthy eating habits that are not in line with one's Prakriti greatly raise the risk of diabetes, heart disease, cancer, and many other lifestyle disorders. Bad eating habits include overindulging in some meals, not getting enough nourishment, and consuming too much processed or refined foods and saturated fats. This affects people at both ends of the socioeconomic spectrum, and both groups suffer from various ailments. One characteristic that distinguishes urbanisation, growth, and advancement is sedentary lives.^[15] This is a major factor in the Dosha's malfunction, especially in the Pitta Prakriti and Kapha, which increases the risk of lifestyle diseases and chronic conditions including high blood pressure and cholesterol. These conditions may then worsen diabetes, heart disease, strokes, obesity, and other conditions. Additionally, it can increase your risk of developing a number of other ailments and make you feel more anxious and agitated. Although Kapha shares traits with fatty and lipid tissues, people with Kapha Prakriti are more likely to suffer from hyperlipidaemic diseases. Since obesity significantly raises the risk of several illnesses, such as diabetes, hypertension, and sleep apnoea, it is a significant issue in modern culture.^[16] The traits of psycho-somatic processes and vata are comparable. Consequently, Vata Prakriti is thought to be more vulnerable to malnourishment and ailments associated with stress. As it worsens and raises the risk of conditions like obesity, heart disease, diabetes, asthma, Alzheimer's disease, accelerated ageing, and gastrointestinal diseases, stress has a noticeable physical impact in addition to its emotional and mental effects. Stress and anxiety not only make it hard to unwind and sleep well, but they can also lead to a variety of additional issues.^[17]

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the assessment of prakriti analysis is crucial for the diagnosis, prognosis, treatment, and prevention of many complex conditions, as well as for understanding the patient's physical and mental characteristics. Different metabolic processes are linked to *pitta, kapha, and vata prakriti*. According to Ayurveda, *vata* is thought to have a varied metabolism, *pitta* is quick, and *kapha* is slow. A number of studies have tried to link specific types of prakriti to different metabolic processes in the body. For everyone to be healthy and achieve their goals in life, it is therefore essential to comprehend or analyse Prakriti.

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